

ISic1555

I.Sicily inscription 1555

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

stele

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8732

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]δης

2. [---]υ

2a. []

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284798

EDR 105644

EDCS 41300029

PHI 175620

Bibliography

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo.
Sikelika 6. Palermo. At 25

Di Stefano, C.A. 1984. Lilibeo. Testimonianze archeologiche dal IV sec a.C. al V
sec. d.C.. Palermo. At 169

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